

THE CARPENTRIES

The Carpentries Strategic Plan for 2020-2025 Evaluation Report

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Introduction

In 2020, The Carpentries released its first [Strategic Plan \(2020-2025\)](#), envisioning a path for the future of the organisation over the course of five years. The strategic plan presented six broad goals, each with its rationale and underlying objectives, to serve as touchpoints to guide the organisation's governance, Core Team and the broader community's activities in that period.

The six goals identified were to:

- Build regional and local capacity to empower sustainable communities.
- Intentionally incorporate equity, inclusion, and accessibility to support a diverse community.
- Provide opportunities for growth and professional development of our volunteers and Core Team.
- Facilitate the creation and maintenance of relevant, high-quality, Community-curated curricula.
- Strengthen organisational structure and capacity to be strategic and responsive.
- Advocate for our values and vision to empower more people to work with data and software.

This report showcases how The Carpentries governance, Core Team, and volunteer community excelled in realising their goals for the reporting period. In most instances, the goals achieved during the strategic plan period continue to positively impact how the organisation's structures and community function.

For our first strategic plan, we did not define upfront the metrics by which to measure the Objectives and Key Results (OKRs) under each goal in order to know when the goal has been achieved. The Carpentries Core Team carried out this task retrospectively, before delving into an assessment of the outcomes of each goal and the overall strategic plan. We are currently in the process of operationalising our strategic plan for 2026-2028, and identifying metrics for its goals prior to the strategic plan's implementation is an integral part in that process.

Method

The development of this strategic plan was guided by a collaborative, data-driven process led by The Carpentries nine Core Team members. We were divided into three small groups, with each group focusing on two of the strategic goals. This structure allowed us to work efficiently, ensure comprehensive coverage of each goal, and maintain shared accountability throughout the process.

To approach the work systematically, each group followed a consistent five-step workflow:

- **Define Objectives and Key Results (OKRs):** Each team articulated clear, measurable objectives aligned with each strategic goal, identifying specific outcomes and success indicators.
- **Establish Baseline Data:** We reviewed existing reports, dashboards, and communications to determine starting points for each metric.
- **Gather Evidence of Outcomes (Current Data):** Groups identified and pulled relevant data from internal databases, surveys, program records, and external benchmarks to assess current performance.
- **Measure Progress Using Available Data:** Teams analysed the gathered information to evaluate progress toward the defined objectives, focusing on clarity, consistency, and data reliability.
- **Comparative Analysis of Strategic Goals Progress:** Finally, teams compared results across strategic goals to identify trends, gaps, and opportunities for improvement.

After each step, the Core Team reconvened to share findings, allowing members to provide feedback, surface additional insights, and make recommendations before moving forward. This iterative process ensured alignment and collective ownership throughout the planning effort.

Once all steps were completed, the entire Core Team met to review all findings and reach consensus on the final data sources and metrics. Through facilitated discussions, we confirmed the credibility and sustainability of selected indicators, ensuring the plan was grounded in strong evidence and clear evaluation methods.

Findings

Goal 1: Build regional and local capacity to empower sustainable communities.

Our community is volunteer-based and our Core Team needs to ensure that we support them to become sustainable and remain effective. Throughout the strategic plan period, we met key objectives on capacity building and developing community programs, resources, materials, and engagement to deliver this goal.

We first piloted the Community Feedback Facilitator program in 2020, with a [cohort of 10 community members](#), in The Carpentries' methodology for leadership, code of conduct, equity and inclusion, and communication. During this process, we recognised that this program needed to be expanded and it formally became our [Community Development Program \(CDP\) in 2021](#). The CDP empowered local leadership, including mentorship for new leaders and highlighting communication channels for connecting local leaders. To support explicit training in our values, code of conduct, and equity, inclusion, and accessibility, we developed and

published our [Toolkit of IDEAS](#), gathering contributions from 48 community members. The toolkit reached 3,000 downloads and 5,000 views to date.

Our community events are a foundation for how we build The Carpentries together. We hosted seven [CarpentryConnect community events](#), either in-person or online, resulting in a range of events in [South Africa](#), [Germany](#), the [UK](#), the USA, and other locations. We also developed a [CarpentryConnect Planning Kit](#), containing resources, templates, and documentation, to enable local event planners to run their CarpentryConnect events. This allows them to share experiences and learn from one another, locally, regionally, and globally.

We needed to ensure that our global communities were supported appropriately by Regional Coordinators, Instructor Trainers, and other community roles that work in a location-specific manner. To help centralise information about our regional communities to foster engagement, planning and collaboration, we created a [subcommunity registry](#) with contributions from 22 community members. In 2022 we initiated, and have continued to host, [quarterly meetings](#) to engage with local community members and member organisations, facilitating local and regional engagement.

Our Member Organisations act as community hubs for training, development and community building. To support Members in setting up and maintaining these hubs, we provided reports and recommendations for building local capacity for training and community; guidance for establishing an equitable, inclusive, and accessible culture of learning; and information about getting involved in the global Carpentries community. We developed a [slide deck to onboard new Member Organisations](#), ensuring consistency in the distribution of information. Since 2024, we have onboarded 20 new Member Organisations using these resources. We also produced quarterly membership newsletters to inform Member Organisations about relevant events, resources, and strategy. To date, we have delivered five newsletters to all membership contacts, with an average of 139 recipients, a 58% open rate, and 12% click-through rate.

Finally, we developed and enacted a plan for strategically engaging libraries and research computing centres to act as Carpentries hubs for their institutions. We delivered this through Centrally-Organised Workshops and Instructor Training events, aiming to initiate and expand their institutional capacity for Carpentries pedagogy. This occurred over one pilot phase and a subsequent post-pilot “rollout” phase (see respective tables below), and resulted in over 50 new Instructors within those communities.

Table 1: Strategic Engagement with Libraries - Pilot

Memberships	Workshops Hosted	Instructors Trained	Instructors Certified
Texas State Library and Archives Commission	4	4	1
California State University San Marcos	1	0	0

California State University Humboldt	0	0	0
Lebanon Public Libraries	1	5	5
Ohio State	4	6	4
Total	10	15	10

Table 2: Strategic Engagement with Libraries - Post Pilot

Memberships	Instructors Trained	Instructors Certified
New England Software Carpentry Library Consortium	50	36
National Health Services Library and Knowledge Services	0	0
Auraria Library	0	0
Texas Digital Library	6	5
Texas State Library and Archives Commission	4	1
Total	60	42

Goal 2: Intentionally incorporate equity, inclusion, and accessibility to support a diverse community.

Over the course of the strategic plan period, we achieved substantial progress across key equity, inclusion, and accessibility (EIA) indicators. We formally established our first Equity Council, consisting of nine members, five of whom represented minority-serving institutions. The Council met four times during its term to advance its objectives. Although we hosted an Equity Council Summit, we did not meet our goal of holding at least one open engagement opportunity between the Council and the broader community.

Our engagement with [Understood for All](#) in 2022 led to a shift in our operational processes, which previously lacked structured approaches to equity, inclusion and accessibility. To date, we have successfully embedded these values across our operational processes. Information about this shift is included under Goal 5.

We partnered with more than five under-resourced institutions and community organisations across 13 countries to co-develop and deliver tailored training. These countries include Argentina, Canada, Colombia, Denmark, Germany, Ireland, Kenya, Lebanon, Namibia, Peru, South Africa, the United Kingdom, and the United States. We onboarded Instructors and Instructor Trainers from under-resourced institutions and new geographical regions to lead

workshops and training sessions. Additionally, [The Carpentries Offline](#) was formally integrated as an official subcommunity during the strategic plan period.

We met our goal of translating at least three community resources into non-English languages, supporting the community in translating lessons into Italian, Japanese, Spanish, and Ukrainian. In accessibility, we launched an accessibility fund, created and shared an accessibility roadmap for community feedback, provided closed captioning guidance for hosting community sessions, created the Toolkit of IDEAS for accessible learning environments, and added accessibility checks to workshop planning workflows. Additionally, we initiated an email conversation and formal meeting with a member of the Deaf and Hard of Hearing community to better understand their training needs.

We also prioritised and implemented several accessibility enhancements to lessons, resources, and workflows. Notable efforts included redesigning the lesson infrastructure, revamping the Instructor checkout process, streamlining Instructor sign-up through our AMY platform, and investing in [Glosario](#), our multilingual data science glossary. We also developed user guides to simplify community engagement with our systems (e.g., [AMY Community Users Guide](#), [Etherpad users guide](#)).

Culturally responsive teaching principles were embedded into three modules of the Instructor Training curriculum, including updated reading lists, bias-testing resources, and more inclusive teaching materials. Additionally, we hosted two interactive sessions on implementing our Toolkit of IDEAS, including presentations at csv.conf,v7 and CarpentryCon 2022.

Goal 3: Provide opportunities for growth and professional development of our volunteers and Core Team.

For Goal 3, we aimed to create new and enhance existing opportunities for growth and professional development of our volunteers and Core Team. The beginning of our strategic plan coincided with the Covid-19 pandemic, and as immediate aims we wanted to develop and publish an Instructor Training bonus module related to teaching online, and then deliver that bonus module to at least 50 community members. Prior to 2020, all of our Centrally-Organised Workshops were in-person, and the pandemic gave us an opportunity to rethink this. We published an [Instructor Training bonus module](#) related to teaching online, and 131 Instructors attended between October 2020 and December 2021. Today, The Carpentries offers the majority of our workshops online.

Prior to 2020, we did not host specific training opportunities to prepare Instructors to use our workshop website template; even though this was included in the Instructor Training curriculum, there was not always enough time to cover this section in detail. As part of our strategic plan, we wanted to provide at least 10 training opportunities to prepare at least 50 Instructors to use our workshop website template. We exceeded this goal by hosting 21 sessions between July 2023 and April 2025, which were attended by a total of 147 participants.

Rather than focusing solely on introducing new interventions, our Strategic Plan also aimed to identify processes and practices that were already part of our community, and consciously maintain them. One such practice was the incorporation of debriefing sessions at every Instructor Trainer meeting for continued learning, allowing Instructor Trainers to reflect on successes and learn from challenges of hosting a training event. This was already done prior to the start of our strategic plan, and is now an integral part of our monthly Instructor Trainer meetings.

We also developed, documented, and piloted an onboarding process for at least three committee leadership roles: the Executive Council (now Board of Directors), Curriculum Advisors, and Lesson Program Governance Committees. Prior to the strategic plan, these roles had loosely structured onboarding processes. Each of these roles now has a handbook in the [Carpentries Handbook](#), containing a detailed onboarding section: the [Board of Directors Handbook](#), the [Curriculum Advisor's Handbook](#), and the [Lesson Program Governance Committees Handbook](#).

To support our governance to work more practically and efficiently, in July 2021 we [formed standing committees within the Executive Council governance structure](#). Up until that period, this group did not have a standing committee structure, and functioned as one collective unit. Standing committees have evolved since the first iteration, but have remained a feature within our governance structure, as reflected in [the roles and responsibilities of our current Board of Directors](#).

Furthermore, we created a formal recognition process for the community roles of Instructor, Maintainer, Community Facilitator, and Instructor Trainers Leadership Group. Prior to 2020, the Instructor and Maintainer roles were already recognised roles within the community, but they did not have a formal onboarding and recognition structure. The Instructor Trainers Leadership role was created in 2021. In 2024, the Group was [renamed the Instructor Trainers Leadership Committee \(ITLC\)](#). The Handbook for the role is currently in development. We also created, and subsequently discontinued a Community Facilitator role.

Goal 3 shared some overlap with Goal 1, which aimed to build regional and local capacity to empower sustainable communities. Under Goal 3, with the aim to increase access as well as the visibility of our volunteer communities, we created [a centralised database for subcommunities](#) to register with The Carpentries. Knowledge of our regional, local, and special-interest subcommunities was not systematised, and we were aware of them informally. However, as mentioned under Goal 1, the subcommunity registry was then created in July 2023, and by April 2025 it had 22 subcommunities registered. The registered subcommunities are categorised into 10 regional, seven local, and five special interest subcommunities.

Members of the Carpentries Core Team are also members of The Carpentries community at large. As such, Goal 3 of the strategic plan also paid focus to providing opportunities for growth and professional development for our Core Team. To this end, we ran a professional

development series for Team Leads, which covered topics such as agenda setting, organisational goal setting, mentorship, reprioritisation, and delegation. The professional development series used resources developed by the [Management Center](#) and provided through support from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative. We also engaged [Tara Robertson Consulting](#), an expert in inclusive leadership, to lead training on neurodiversity, deaf inclusion and culture, and meeting facilitation. We provided time for and encouraged team members to take up external opportunities for coaching - four team members received support from an executive coach, while another team member participated in a communications training cohort organised by the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative.

In addition to providing professional development for Team Leads, we developed a Supervisor onboarding program to prepare members of the Core Team to serve in a supervisory role. Our goal for this program was to empower enough Core Team members to serve as Supervisors to bring our supervisory ratio to 3:1 or lower. In January 2020, three Supervisors served a team of nine, supervising between two and four team members each. Supervisory ratios climbed to a peak of 9:1 in 2022, and onboarding was introduced in January 2023. Currently, a team of five Supervisors manages a total of nine Core Team members, each supervising between one and three team members.

Goal 4: Facilitate the creation and maintenance of relevant, high-quality, community-curated curricula.

The Carpentries made strides towards the sustainable development and maintenance of community curated curricula in this strategic plan period. Before the reporting period began, we had no active process for onboarding and offboarding Maintainers, and support for the role was limited to sparse documentation. During the strategic plan period, we developed and established an annual cycle of onboarding and offboarding for the volunteer Maintainers of Data Carpentry, Library Carpentry, and Software Carpentry lessons, providing a structured pathway for new Maintainers to become engaged, learn the skills they need for the role, and connect with their co-Maintainers. The process includes a low-effort mechanism for existing Maintainers to step away from the role and for the Curriculum Team to estimate Maintainer capacity across lessons, aiding with strategic planning and outreach efforts related to each yearly Maintainer Onboarding cycle.

A new role (Maintainer Community Lead) was established, and a curriculum for Maintainer onboarding was updated and delivered to 123 new Maintainers during the strategic plan period (Table 3). The content of the [Maintainer handbook](#) was expanded and updated and, later in the reporting period, Maintainer onboarding was supplemented with a GitHub Skill-up in recognition of the need for new Maintainers to build additional knowledge, skill, and confidence with the platform hosting our lesson repositories.

Table 3: Maintainers Onboarded 2020-2024

Year	New Maintainers Onboarded
2020	30
2021	18
2022	30
2023	19
2024	26
Total	123

To further support the Maintainer community and strengthen the community’s ownership of curricula, we established the new role of Lesson Program Governor and reinforced the role of Curriculum Advisor. Tasked with guiding the development of Data Carpentry, Library Carpentry, and Software Carpentry curricula, Curriculum Advisors coordinate with Maintainers to ensure the enduring relevance and accuracy of Carpentries lessons. Lesson Program Governors oversee the strategy of the lesson program, advocate for it, and represent it as points of contact from the lesson program community for the Core Team, Board of Directors, and wider Carpentries community (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Lesson Program Governance

Each Curriculum Advisory Committee and Governance Committee has a corresponding mailing list for internal and external communication, and is supported by a structured onboarding process for members, and a dedicated Core Team liaison. Community members in either role can refer to a dedicated [handbook](#) detailing the role, its responsibilities, and relevant resources to help them function. One particularly valuable resource, developed during the strategic plan period, is [a rubric describing the division of responsibilities](#) and recommended points of discussion between Curriculum Advisors and Maintainers.

In October of 2023, we partnered with NASA Tops to pilot one Instructor Training event tailored to the unique needs of the NASA Tops learners. This training focused exclusively on the Carpentries' pedagogical approach and intentionally excluded content related to teaching within the Carpentries or the process of becoming a certified Carpentries Instructor. Building on this pilot, the Workshops and Instruction Team plans to develop a variant of the Instructor Training curriculum starting Q3 2025 (July–September) for learners who are interested in The Carpentries pedagogy but do not intend to teach for The Carpentries. Up until this point, Instructor Training has been designed exclusively for preparing Instructors to teach Carpentries workshops.

Community members were empowered to develop new lessons together through dedicated support for The Carpentries Incubator program. The number of lesson repositories hosted in

The Carpentries Incubator grew from four to more than 150 during the strategic plan reporting period (Figure 2). Collaborative lesson development in the Incubator was supported with new and improved documentation, support with communications (e.g. to attract contributions and feedback from pilot workshops), training via The Carpentries Collaborative Lesson Development Training program, and the introduction of a new, accessible infrastructure for building lesson websites, The Carpentries Workbench.

Figure 2: Community Curated Lessons

Community members were encouraged to indicate the development maturity of their lessons through a “life cycle” described in the community handbook (Figure 3). Release of lessons was documented in the community handbook, supported by the Core Team, and simplified considerably with the introduction of the Workbench. The lesson release process is being further enhanced with [the ongoing integration of Citation File Format into the lesson infrastructure](#).

Figure 3: Lesson Maturity for Curated Lessons

Lesson development in the Incubator was complemented by the establishment of a structured process of community peer review in The Carpentries Lab. Reviews in the Lab take place in

publicly-visible issue threads on GitHub, supported by documentation and templates for authors, editors, and reviewers. Editors and reviewers provide feedback to further improve lessons and ensure that they are ready to be taught by the wider Carpentries Instructor community. Lesson authors were [further empowered through a collaboration with the Journal of Open Source Education \(JOSE\)](#), which provides a fast-track process to journal publication of an article about a lesson already approved for inclusion in The Carpentries Lab. At the end of the strategic plan reporting period, eight lessons had passed peer review and entered The Carpentries Lab, six of which had also been published in the Journal of Open Source Education (JOSE).

The overall experience of contributors was improved through the development and publication of accessible contribution templates (such as structured templates to aid the submission of issues and pull requests to lesson repositories) and documentation to support novice contributions (such as tutorial videos), and the curation of various beginner-friendly contribution opportunities (such as an expanded list of issues identified as suitable for first-time contributors across repositories for official Carpentries lessons and those in the Incubator). Table 4 summarises the resources developed to support contributors during the strategic plan period.

Table 4: Resources Developed to Support Contributors

Type of resource/opportunity	Number at beginning of strategic plan period	Number developed during strategic plan period	Link to example of new resource/opportunity
Accessible contribution templates	3	10	https://github.com/datacarpentry/.github
Documentation resources to support novice contributions	3	6	https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=f9K5wYq0dQM&t=23s
Beginner-friendly contribution opportunities	3	8	https://carpentries.org/lessons/help_wanted/

Goal 5: Strengthen organisational structure and capacity to be strategic and responsive.

On 1 February 2025, [The Carpentries officially became an independent 501\(c\)\(3\) non-profit organisation](#). As we prepared for our shift to independent 501(c)(3) status, we prioritised developing organisational structures to support our Core Team, improve the efficiency of our work, and empower individual team members to make decisions within their spheres of authority. In support of this goal, we developed the following resources, which were collaboratively developed by affected team members and are periodically reviewed and updated for continued use.

- Guiding Principles for Decision Making: Categorises different types of activities carried out by the Core Team and lays out the [MOCHA](#) roles (manager, owner, consulted, helper, approver) for each. This provides clear guidance for who is authorised to make different types of decisions and enables individual Core Team members to carry out their work with confidence and autonomy.
- Team Roles and Responsibilities: Provides a summary of the overall remit of individual programmatic teams within the Core Team, along with a detailed list of responsibilities for each team member and the percentage of their time dedicated to that team. Also includes information about decision making responsibilities within that team's area of activity.
- Decision Tracker: Documents important decisions made across all teams, including information about decision maker(s), dates, and links to meeting notes or other resources. Serves as a stable reference point for historical decisions.
- Competency Model: Defines the skills and behaviours required for different Core Team roles. Provides transparency about job requirements and serves as a tool for decision making around hiring, salaries, promotions, and terminations.

Also as part of our shift to independent status, we had the opportunity to develop new policies and practices related to leave policies and benefit offerings. In developing leave policies, we received support from the Chan Zuckerberg Initiative to engage the consulting group [LaCire](#) to develop human-centered leave policies in accordance with current best practices. As a result of this consultation, we made the following adjustments to our leave policies:

- Extended parental leave, regardless of gender, to 16 weeks of full pay.
- Extended bereavement leave to cover the loss of any loved one, including non-family members, pregnancy loss, and pets.
- Implemented extended sick leave as a separate allowance from standard sick leave, to provide space for recovery from surgeries, mental health treatment, and other extended health-related leave.
- Pooled bank holiday allowance (federal or locality) allowance with personal holiday allowance (vacation) to give each team member maximum autonomy in observing holidays of personal or cultural significance.
- Provided a bank of additional leave to be used to fulfill civic responsibilities (e.g. jury duty, military reserve duty, school appearances).
- Established a commitment to providing additional leave to Core Team members employed outside of the United States in cases where statutory requirements in their locality are below those provided to our United States team members.

Prior to new policy development, satisfaction levels with available sick days and vacation days were moderately high (2.3 and 2.4 respectively, on a scale of 1-5, with 1 being highly satisfied). Satisfaction with our bereavement policy however, which provided minimal leave for specific, immediate family members, was low (4.0 out of 5). After introduction of new policies, satisfaction with sick and vacation allowances increased by 0.4 points each, and satisfaction with bereavement policy increased by 3 points.

Table 5: Level of satisfaction with policies before and after the 1 February 2025 transition to independent non-profit status. Lower numbers represent higher satisfaction.

	Number of vacation days (PTO) available	Number of sick days available	Bereavement policy
Before Transition	2.3	2.4	4.0
After Transition	1.9	2.0	1.0
Change	-0.4	-0.4	-3.0

Along with evaluating our leave policies, we also undertook to benchmark our salary ranges and ensure their alignment with industry standards. We used information from the Fairpay for Northern California Nonprofits compensation survey, which provides salary data for 40,000 employees of 779 nonprofit organisations operating in California, USA. Although our team is spread across the globe, at time of analysis, we were headquartered in Oakland, California through our fiscal sponsor, Community Initiatives. The major outcomes of this analysis were as follows:

- Increased number of salary levels from four to ten to improve granularity.
- Removed overlap in salary brackets between position levels.
- Set target salary levels to 50th-90th percentile of similar positions in organisations of similar size and budget.

To adapt locally collected data (California, USA) for the needs of our global team, we implemented two adjustment measures for Core Team members based outside of the United States. Firstly we incorporated a percentage adjustment to total compensation based on comparative cost of living figures between the United States and the local country of employment. Secondly, we implemented an annual adjustment for changes in currency conversion rates, with adjustments always being made in the favor of the Core Team member.

In alignment with our Core Value of "Access for All", we also undertook a comprehensive evaluation of our hiring and onboarding processes. We partnered with the US-based nonprofit organisation, [Understood for All](#), to undertake this analysis, and hired a full-time Accessibility Manager to help implement recommendations and educate the team and community about accessibility. Some changes resulting from this work include:

- Implementing an accommodations policy for the Core Team and an accommodations process for community members.
- Adding disability-focused job boards to our list of places to post new job opportunities.
- Focusing job descriptions on essential functions.
- Proactively offering accommodations throughout the interviewing process.
- Aligning interview questions to the essential functions of the job and providing questions in advance.
- Incorporating explicit discussion of working styles and preferences during the onboarding process.

In the interests of organisational efficiency, and to enable Core Team members to take time off without worrying about interruptions of core operations, we undertook to document our existing workflows and ensure cross training of at least two team members for each essential operational function. This process began in the early days of Covid-19, due to the threat of sudden gaps in Core Team coverage due to illness and/or caregiving responsibilities. We established a list of 55 essential operational tasks. As of November 2023, 63% of those tasks had documented workflows to enable them to be performed by someone other than their normal team member. By April 2025, we had reached 88% documentation coverage of our core processes. We continue to update and refine existing documentation and to create workflows for the remaining 12% of core functions.

Another key area of organisational capacity development focused on diversifying our revenue streams. During the strategic plan period, we secured funding from six new granting agencies as well as continuing or recurring support from previous granting bodies. In addition, we received two corporate sponsorships and grew our individual donor pool from sixteen individuals to 120 unique individual donors during this period.

We also focused on strengthening our operational reliance, which is the portion of operating expenses that can be met through programmatic income (e.g. workshops and Membership fees). Over the strategic plan period, we were able to increase our operating reliance from 41% in 2020 to 70% in 2024. This was accomplished largely through staff reductions at the end of 2023, along with a corresponding redirection of remaining staff time towards core program support.

Figure 4: Operating Reliance Over Time

Goal 6: Advocate for our values and vision to empower more people to work with data and software.

Advocacy for the Carpentries through community empowerment is a critical component of our strategy. That empowerment comes in a variety of forms, including submitting and being partners on grant activities, the creation of resources and materials for community members to

use when speaking to others about The Carpentries, geographically relevant support mechanisms so communities can build effectively in their localities, writing and publishing articles about our work and the work of others, and serving in official capacities on boards and committees of other organisations.

Throughout this period, we have identified speaking and presenting opportunities for Core Team, governance, and community members that are strategically appropriate to strengthen the visibility of The Carpentries and model our values. We delivered [various](#) keynote addresses and talks, attended collaboration meetings, presented posters, managed booths, and hosted a hackathon. We also supported [six CarpentryConnect events](#), across Australia, Germany, New Zealand, and South Africa.

Table 6: Advocacy and Community Empowerment

Event	Frequency
Delivered Keynotes	5
Hosted Collaboration Meetings	2
Presented Posters	2
Managed Booth	1
Hosted Hackathon	1
Delivered Talks	42

Our [Community Handbook](#) serves as a central reference point, providing easy access to detailed information about our processes, policies, and procedures. To better support our advocacy efforts, our communications-focused resources within the handbook needed an overhaul, so our team updated several communication resources and guidelines and created a [dedicated handbook section](#).

To improve the onboarding experience for lesson developers and Maintainers, as well as those interested in the content and focus of each program, slide decks were created for each lesson program: [Data Carpentry](#), [Library Carpentry](#), and [Software Carpentry](#). We also created a [template slide deck](#) for The Carpentries community to use, which includes standardised content on our policies, governance, and community engagement. In addition, to build on our financial sustainability and capacity, we developed a template and [six one-pagers](#) to provide useful summaries about the benefits and opportunities within The Carpentries. These focused more on advocacy towards organisations and memberships to highlight key information about our training programmes, workshops, and the organisation in general. Finally, we updated [The Carpentries' historical timeline](#) to include the most recent changes to the organisation, improving transparency.

Figure 5: The updated 2025 Brief History of The Carpentries, depicting a timeline of key events from inception in 1998 to the current day.

We intentionally reached out to communities aligned with The Carpentries to create, build, and foster relationships and develop synergies. These efforts involved extensive collaboration through joint grant funding applications and awards, as well as communications and community sessions, and the development of new outreach initiatives.

The Carpentries developed a new detailed membership outreach workflow to engage with organisations that have previously been involved in The Carpentries community, but had a membership that has since lapsed. Prior to this development, we had no formal outreach process to encourage past Member Organisations to renew their membership. To date, this effort has led to the reinstatement of 27 lapsed Memberships, amounting to \$187,000 USD in recouped revenue.

Grant funding supports not just the internal functioning of The Carpentries organisation but also collaborative community efforts to meet our collective data science and education goals. The Carpentries collaborated with over 30 organisations, either providing letters of support and/or submitting grants collectively with other organisations, such as: The Carpentries 2.0: Scaling

Data and Software Skills Training across the US with California Digital Library (CDL) at the University of California Office of the President (UCOP); and Empowering Collaborative Lesson Development for Open Data Science Education with Morehouse College.

Working with our community to improve understanding of topics closely related to our own goals took the form of collaboration on mutually relevant community sessions and blog posts. Five of our online event highlights were:

- Exploring collaborations: Opportunities for data sharing and data skills training across organisations advocating for open science, 5 October 2023, 46 attendees
- The benefits of participatory live coding: a research exploration, 7 November 2023, 16 attendees
- Searching and Accessing NASA Earthdata with Python 14 November 2023, 41 attendees
- Unlocking Inclusivity, 13 December 2023, 18 attendees
- Tips and Resources for Writing Successful and Impactful Grant Proposals, 20 December 2023, 11 attendees

Following the exodus of scientists from X (then, Twitter), in collaboration with rOpenSci, we developed a [Mastodon Quick Start Guide](#) to help break down barriers for our community members interested in adopting Mastodon as a social media platform.

Published articles are a formal way to build our community standing and encourage discussion. We wrote and influenced a number of position papers related to training and empowering people to work with data and software:

- Two open access articles:
 - van der Walt A, Martin K, Panji S, Trusler A, Vaccari M, van Heusden P (2025) Research Software: A Key (Neglected) Component of the Digital Research Infrastructure Ecosystem (V1.0). *AfricArXiv*. <http://africarxiv.ubuntunet.net/handle/1/1845>
 - Nederbragt A, Harris RM, Hill AP, Wilson G (2020) Ten quick tips for teaching with participatory live coding. *PLoS Comput Biol* 16(9): e1008090. <https://doi.org/10.1371/journal.pcbi.1008090>
- Three articles about community experiences and The Carpentries:
 - Sackmann A, Ngo L, Smith E, Coleman M (2024) Bridging Data Communities: Interoperability through inclusive, cross-institutional collaboration. *Journal of eScience Librarianship* 13 (3): e970. <https://doi.org/10.7191/jeslib.970>
 - Nelson, Adam Ross (2023) The Carpentries: Diversifying Data + Tech. *Medium* (17 Apr 2023). <https://pub.towardsai.net/the-carpentries-diversifying-data-tech-291ebeb6816c>
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 - van der Walt A, Steyn J, Trusler A, van Zaanen M (2023) Challenges and Opportunities of Digital Humanities Training in South Africa: Moving Beyond the Silos. Digital Humanities Workshops (1st Ed. ISBN: 9781003301097) <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/chapters/oa-edit/10.4324/9781003301097-7/challenges-opportunities-digital-humanities-training-south-africa-anelda-van-der-walt-ju-an-steyn-angelique-trusler-menno-van-zaanen>
 - Irving D, Hertweck K, Johnston L, Ostblom J, Wickham C, Wilson G (2021) Research Software Engineering with Python: Building software that makes research possible. <https://third-bit.com/py-rse/>

We recognise that advocacy needs to happen from within too, so we encourage both our Carpentries Core Team and community members to serve on advisory boards of other organisations. We aim to provide guidance and advocacy in areas key to The Carpentries mission and vision, and respond to requests for comments in these areas. As such, the Core Team served on [25 organising committees, boards of other organisations and other community engagement efforts](#). These included but were not limited to:

- iDigBio, External Advisory Board Member
- Banbury Life Sciences Training, Organizing Committee Member
- Planning for Open Grants, Advisory Committee Member
- CS&S Event Fund, Advisory Committee Member
- Agricultural Genome to Phenome Initiative (AG2PI), Scientific Advisory Board Member
- Reproducibility for Everyone (R4E), Advisory Committee Member
- Open Research Funders Group (ORFG), Equitable Working Group Member

Open science has transformed how research is conducted, shared, and reused. Yet the organisations at the heart of this transformation are often left vulnerable, underfunded, and disconnected from one another. To move from simply surviving to truly thriving, we developed a strategic alliance of five leading open science organisations -- The Carpentries, [OLS](#), [rOpenSci](#), [pyOpenSci](#), and [PREreview](#)) -- to [chart a collective path forward](#) funded by The Navigation Fund.

Moving forward, we are planning a strategic, in-person convening of leadership from these organisations to focus on:

- Shared financial sustainability: Developing collective, value-aligned models for funding and resource generation.
- Collaborative engagement strategies: Designing systems that strengthen and connect our communities across roles, regions, and lived experiences.
- Equity-centered design: Ensuring accessibility, usability, and meaningful participation for all involved.

Facilitated by [Wildly Open](#), we are excited to explore and better understand what is (and isn't) working, and then build durable models for collaboration and sustainability. We aim to deliver:

- A coordinated sustainability strategy that reflects the shared values of our organisations.
- A funder-facing pitch to mobilise resources in support of this strategy.
- Stronger ties among our organisations that extend beyond the convening to create lasting impact.

This convening is not an isolated event. It is the first step in scaling a movement that reimagines how values-driven open science organisations can grow together, share resources, and strengthen the ecosystem we collectively serve. By working together, we can ensure that the future of open science is not only innovative, but also equitable, sustainable, and resilient.

Future Work

We are proud of everything that The Carpentries community and Core Team have accomplished in the past five years in service to our first strategic plan. We are now in the process of operationalising our strategic plan for 2026 - 2028, which focuses on the following four goals:

- Foster the development of a new curriculum in an emerging domain to promote efficient, open, and reproducible research practices, such as research software engineering (RSEng) and artificial intelligence (AI).
- Formalise a stable, sustainable revenue framework that prioritises flexibility and supports equity in communities with limited access to Carpentries programming.
- Establish a Community Scalability Model using linguistic, geographical, and community engagement metrics to predict capacity and enable equitable scaling of core programs, focusing on geographically diverse communities.
- Empower Subcommunity Leaders to act as multilingual advocates for The Carpentries, enabling coordination of local training and distribution of open source lessons in their region's primary language(s).

Thank You

The work detailed in this report would not have been possible without the contributions of our many community members - including our Board of Directors, Subcommunity Coordinators, Code of Conduct Committee, Curriculum Advisors, Instructors, Instructor Trainers, Learners, Lesson Development Trainers, Lesson Maintainers, Lesson Program Governors, Member Organisations, Trainer Leadership Committee, Workshop Helpers and Hosts, and all of our other amazing community members! We also extend gratitude to all of the previous members of The Carpentries Core Team, along with our independent contractors, whose work was foundational to achieving the aims detailed here.

We would also like to recognise the monetary support The Carpentries has received from our funders - including the American Astronomical Society, Alfred P. Sloan Foundation, Andrew W. Mellon Foundation, Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, Code for Science and Society, Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation, Institute of Museum and Library Services, Mozilla Foundation, Network of

the National Library of Medicine, University of California Office of the President, and University of California Berkeley; our sponsors - Jump Recruits and Posit; and our more than 120 individual donors.

Last, but not least, we extend gratitude to Community Initiatives, who served as our fiscal sponsor throughout this period, and to CxORE, who provide administrative and back office support for our independent 501(c)3 organisation.

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